

Plan of analysis

The association between prenatal maternal Selenium concentration and mental health in early childhood

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Objectives:

Primary: To examine the association between maternal Se concentration and mental health problems as measured by the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) assessed at 4 years of age in a mother-child cohort from Nepal.

Secondary: To describe the psychometrics of SDQ when used in Nepal.

Hypothesis

Overall: Prenatal maternal Selenium concentration is associated with mental health scores in Nepalese children in early childhood.

Specific: The original 5 factors structure and bifactors models of SDQ will provide good fit in the Nepalese sample of children

Data: We will use CISMACH main study ([B12 in pregnancy | UiB](#)) and 4 years follow-up data. We will include all children with data on maternal selenium concentration within 15 weeks of gestation and SDQ data assessed at 4 years of age.

Baseline Demographics for the included sample:

- Age of the mother (Cont)
- Type of family (Nuclear /joint)
- Education of the mother (Below and above grade 10)
- Occupation of the mother (Working / no formal work)
- Socioeconomic status (WAMI)-related variables (Water and sanitation, Assets, Maternal education and Income)
- Maternal anthropometry (Cont)
- Maternal BMI (Cont)

Child-related variables

- Sex (Male/Female)
- Low birthweight (<2500g)
- Gestational age (Cont.)
- Preterm birth (<37 weeks)
- Height of the child at 4 years
- Weight of the child at 4 years
- Weight for height z-score at 4 years

Main exposure: Prenatal plasma Selenium concentration. We will use the Plasma Selenium concentrations within 15 weeks of gestation from pregnant women drawn at the enrollment using plasma samples (Continuous, Dichotomized (< 71.1 µg/L), Tertiles).

Main outcomes: The SDQ score chosen as the main outcome will be based on the results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA).

Secondary outcomes: SDQ subscale scores based on psychometric analysis (CFA)

Covariates:

- WAMI at enrollment (cont)
- Maternal age (cont)

Effect modification:

- Se*Sex

Planned statistical analysis:

Descriptives of SDQ:

We will also present descriptive SDQ scores using Stata. Which SDQ scores that are chosen will be based on the findings from the CFA.

Association between maternal Se concentration and SDQ scores (primary objective)

We will use generalized linear models (GLMs) in Stata program with assuming normal distribution and with an identity link function to examine the association between maternal Se concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$) and the child's SDQ scores (based on the CFA result as continuous outcome).

For binary outcomes, GLMs with a binomial distribution and logit- link function will be estimated to show odds ratios treating maternal Se as continuous. We will also examine the associations between Se concentrations as tertiles or dichotomized and SDQ scores using interaction terms (child sex \times Se) to assess potential effect modification.

Psychometrics of SDQ (Secondary objective):

Cronbach's alpha or Omega (ω) will be used to examine the internal consistency of subscales.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) for the five-factor solution as well as the bifactor model will be done based on the model (Model 2) using JASP ([JASP - A Fresh Way to Do Statistics](#)).

Model 1: Original 5 factors model (Emotional symptoms, Hyperactivity, Conduct problems, Peer problems and Prosocial behavior)

Model 2. CFA using a bifactor model with a general factor (Total difficulties score) and Externalizing (Hyperactivity + Conduct), Internalizing (Emotional + Peer) problems

Psychometrics of SDQ will be evaluated based on the Comparative fit index (CFI) and Root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) for factor structure analysis and Cronbach's alpha or Omega for analyzing internal consistency. We will consider the following ranges to fit the models:

CFI \geq 0.95 \rightarrow Good fit

CFI \geq 0.90 \rightarrow Acceptable fit

CFI < 0.90 → Poor fit

RMSEA ≤ 0.05 → Good fit

RMSEA between 0.05–0.08 → Acceptable fit

Both α and $\omega \geq 0.70$ are considered acceptable

Tables and figures:

Table 1: Baseline demographics and socioeconomic factors

Table 2. Confirmatory Factor Analysis of SDQ with two different factor models

Table 3. Descriptive of SDQ scores and Cronbach's alphas/Omegas for each subscale

Table 4. Association between maternal Selenium concentration (continuous and dichotomized) and SDQ scores of children of Bhaktapur, Nepal at 4 years of age

Table 6. Association between maternal Selenium concentration (Tertiles) and SDQ scores of children of Bhaktapur Nepal at 4 years of age

Figure/Graphs:

Dissemination plan: Will publish the results in a peer-reviewed journal and share the findings summaries in the academic community at LinkedIn and in a daily newspaper under the health chapter

Preregistration: We will also publish the plan of analysis in an online portal (for eg, Zenodo)

DAG (DAGitty v3.1)

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```

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bb="0,0,1,1"
```

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"Maternal Se" [exposure,pos="0.155,0.510"]
"Maternal Se*Sex of the child" [pos="0.407,0.749"]
"SDQ score" [outcome,pos="0.630,0.490"]
"Sex of the child" [pos="0.222,0.777"]
WAMI [pos="0.404,0.251"]
"Maternal Age" -> "Maternal Se"
"Maternal Age" -> "SDQ score"
"Maternal Se" -> "Maternal Se*Sex of the child"
"Maternal Se" -> "SDQ score"
"Maternal Se*Sex of the child" -> "SDQ score"
"Sex of the child" -> "Maternal Se*Sex of the child"
WAMI -> "Maternal Se"
WAMI -> "SDQ score"
}
```